

TANGENT

ETHICS MONITORING. SECOND RELEASE.

D9.10

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https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCjhz4kwEm_sTHj7fE4zXT0A

For further information please visit <http://www.tangent-h2020.eu/>

Executive summary

Adherence to ethical principles and regulations was crucial for the TANGENT successful implementation. This deliverable outlines the updated procedures for conducting research and exploitation in compliance with EU and national ethical standards. We have revised the informed consent templates that must be completed by individuals participating in project activities, workshops, the TANGENT Forum, and traveler behavior modeling. This deliverable also introduces updated measures for effective data management throughout the project, including the handling of personal data. The project implemented various mechanisms for effective data management and protection, as outlined in the Deliverable D9.8. Based on the GDPR privacy policy (Articles 12, 13, and 14) the TANGENT dashboard privacy policy was created and published.

Therefore, the deliverable presented the updated version of the D9.4 submitted in month 12.

Key words

#GDPR, #ethical aspects, #informed consent form, #data management, #data processing, #personal data.

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EU	European Union
UK	United Kingdom
WP	Work Package
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation

1 Introduction

The deliverable D9.10 compiles the updates on ethical measures implemented throughout the TANGENT project to ensure participant rights and, therefore, fulfillment to EU and national regulations and requirements. These measures have been in place since the D9.4 (August 2022). The created TANGENT dashboard privacy policy is based on the GDPR privacy policy: Articles 12, 13, and 14, is presented in this deliverable as well.

Additionally, this report based on three deliverables in month 6 (February 2022), presenting the ethical procedures that will be followed for executing the different research and development activities planned in TANGENT. These deliverables are: a) "D10.1. H - Requirement No. 1"; b) "D10.2. POPD - Requirement No. 2" and c) "D10.3. EPQ - Requirement No. 3". These deliverables have not been modified since the initial release.

2 Informed consent procedures

The informed consent procedures have stayed during the second phase (M19-M39) of the project unmodified.

Below is a brief explanation.

Participants have been involved in activities like the TANGENT Forum, surveys, and travel behavior modeling. Participation was strictly voluntary. Informed consent was required for participation and has been collected. Participants have received detailed information and could withdraw anytime without consequences. Only necessary data has been collected, stored and analysed. Personal data will not be processed without authorization and will adhere to GDPR requirements.

The TANGENT informed consent forms have covered the following:

- All participants must be adults (over 18 years old) in accordance with EU regulations.
- The project does not target vulnerable individuals such as children, discriminated groups, those unable to give consent, minorities, sex workers, etc.
- Participants have the right to be fully informed about the research they are involved in. They shall receive answers to their questions before deciding about participation or data sharing.
- All documents shall be presented in a language and format that is easily understandable.
- The research aims, methods, implications, nature of participation, and potential benefits, risks, or discomforts shall be clearly described.
- Participation is entirely voluntary, and individuals have the right to refuse or withdraw participation at any time without consequences.
- Personal information shall be handled securely and not disclosed to third parties or countries.

Procedures for handling unexpected or incidental findings will be outlined, including whether participants have the right to know about such findings.

During the project the consortium has applied three (3) different informed consents that have been established to address the unique requirements of each action:

- Stakeholders' participating in the TANGENT Forum activities.
- Volunteers participating in the TANGENT Survey.
- Volunteers participating in providing their tracking information.

The templates are available in deliverable "D10.1. H - Requirement No. 1".

During the second period of the project various activities have been carried out, with the TANGENT Advisory Board and workshops with stakeholders in the scope of WP1 for the different Case Studies (Greater Manchester, Rennes and Lisbon). All the participants have completed the Informed Consent Procedure.

3 Data management in TANGENT

The Data management procedure has not been changed since it was established in the TANGENT working documents D9.2 and D9.7. Because the project involved personal data, the consortium adhered to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (EU) 2016/679 and the UK Data Protection Act 2018. Below, this data management approach is briefly presented.

During the project lifetime TANGENT has collected and processed data from various sources to enable precise knowledge and management of mobility flows across different transport modes. This data was applied to support the implementation and integration of innovative mobility solutions, services, and business models.

The TANGENT dashboard privacy policy was created and published, based on the GDPR privacy policy: Articles 12, 13, and 14.

TANGENT dashboard privacy policy

TANGENT project

The European transport faces major challenges in terms of safety, greenhouse gas emissions, traffic congestion and its derived costs. In addition, the development of disruptive technologies and emergence of new mobility solutions generate a revolution in transport network and traffic management. In this context, TANGENT aims to develop new complementary tools for optimising traffic operations in a coordinated and dynamic way from a multimodal perspective and considering automated/non-automated vehicles, passengers and freight transport.

TANGENT will research on advanced techniques on modelling and simulation, such as prediction and simulation models for future demand & supply of transport; optimisation techniques for balancing the demand flows between the means of transport; and users travel behaviour modelling. As a result, a set of applications for decision-making support will be delivered creating a framework for coordinated traffic and transport management, encompassing an enhanced mobility information service and dashboard with associated APIs and advanced functionalities with a two-fold approach: to provide real-time traffic management recommendations and to support Transport Authorities to design network-wide optimal strategies. The framework also aims at supporting a multi-actor cooperation approach for transport network management by enabling communication channels. In this way, the services target to different actors in traffic management.

The results will be tested in three case studies: Rennes Métropole (FR), Lisbon (PT), Great Manchester (UK) and a virtual case study in Athens (EL) with real data from various modes of transport, under different traffic events such as bottlenecks, accidents, pedestrian flow etc.

For further information in TANGENT project, please see: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/955273>

Data protection and confidentiality

The information in the TANGENT dashboard is confidential, and no one else except TANGENT consortium partners will access. The information and data will be managed according to the terms outlined in the Consortium Agreement and TANGENT Data Management Plan.

The information will be used only for the sole purpose of research. It will be stored on a server owned by the University of Deusto and will be kept for a minimum of five years after the end of the project for auditing or reporting purposes by request of the funding agencies.

Contact information from users will be collected to keep contact during project duration. Afterwards, it will be incorporated to a file and kept confidential and will only be used for possible contacts in the future for related projects or activities.

At any time, you can contact Leire Serrano (leire.serrano@deusto.es) to modify or delete your personal data and /or other sensitive information.

Legal information

Data will be handled complying with the applicable regulation at EU level, as well as the national laws applicable:

At EU level:

- *Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation) (OJ L 119, 4.5.2016, p. 1).*

United Kingdom:

UK - Data Protection Act 2018

Further information

If you have any question, please contact: Leire Serrano (leire.serrano@deusto.es)

Additionally, each partner complied with applicable national regulations for personal data processing, regardless of the location.

The consortium collected and processed personal data, including names, email addresses, from individuals involved in TANGENT activities. This data was gathered from participants in the TANGENT forum, workshops, surveys, and other dissemination activities, as well as from a targeted group of travelers in each case study. On top, historical tracking information from Google timelines were used.

TANGENT project has utilized data minimisation principle, data anonymisation/pseudo anonymization and rights and freedoms of the data subjects/research participants.

The measures data protection officer, data processing principles, rights and freedoms of data subjects and research participants, data pseudonymisation and anonymization and informed consents were implemented throughout in the project.

4 Safety and health measures

The safety and health measures (D10.3. EPQ – Requirement No. 3) during project lifetime were continued implementation without modification.

TANGENT team emphasized the importance of adhering to health and safety procedures for all project activities. These procedures must align with relevant local and national guidelines and legislation, including COVID-19 measures. This applies to employees of partner companies, third parties, and participants in workshops and testing activities.

The updated list of regulations applied by TANGENT (more information in D10.3. EPQ – Requirement No. 3):

- The European Framework Directive on Safety and Health at Work ([Directive 89/391 EEC](#)).
- [Health and safety at work, part B2, B3, and C, European Parliament, May 2024,
https://www.europarl.europa.eu/factsheets/en/sheet/56/health-and-safety-at-work](#)
- [The Health and Safety at Work etc. Act 1974](#)

5 Conclusions

Deliverable “D 9.10 Ethics monitoring. Second release”, due in month 38, updates the ethical aspects covered in year 2 and 3 of the project.

This deliverable gives a brief update on the implementation of different measures for complying with ethical aspects during the project. It focuses on procedures related to participant involvement in the project activities, as outlined in informed consent forms. It also provides a brief overview of the consortium's efforts to ensure data minimization, personal data protection, and safety and health measures. The TANGENT dashboard privacy policy which is created and published based on the GDPR privacy policy: Articles 12, 13, and 14, is presented as well.

6 References

TANGENT Grant Agreement (Description of the Action)

Serrano, L. (2022). TANGENT: D9.4. Ethics monitoring. First release.

Serrano, L., Comerio, M., Azzini, A. (2022). TANGENT: D9.2. Data Management Plan. First release.

Serrano, L., Masegosa, A., Metta, S., Comerio, M. (2023). TANGENT: D9.7. Data Management Plan. Second release.

Deliverable D10.1. H - Requirement No. 1, Feb.2022

Deliverable D10.2. POPD - Requirement No. 2, Feb.2022

Deliverable D10.3. EPQ – Requirement No. 3, Feb.2022